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6G Goal-Oriented AI-enabled Learning and Semantic Communication Networks
(6G-GOALS)

Deliverable 7.2

Dissemination and Standardization Action Plan

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Abstract

Deliverable 7.2 represents a public document within the 6G-GOALS EU funded project. The project focuses on semantic and goal-oriented communications, based on AI-enabled architectures, protocols, and services. The deliverable is part of Work Package (WP) 7, which focuses on dissemination, exploitation, and standardisation, specifically tackling Task 7.3 on standardisation.

This document offers a comprehensive standardisation action plan, aiming to map out a roadmap involving pertinent standardisation bodies. It identifies emerging standardisation and pre-standardisation entities, along with industrial associations, and highlights the relevant working groups and activities crucial for 6G-GOALS.

The goal is to leverage the knowledge gained from research and pre-deployment activities within the consortium to steer the development of pertinent standards. Additionally, it seeks to contribute to ongoing discussions within major industry associations regarding the evolution of mobile technologies towards 6G.

Keywords

Semantic communication, goal-oriented communication, AI, 6G, standardisation, industrial association, ETSI, 3GPP, O-RAN, 6G-IA, SNS-JU

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6th Generation
6G-IA	6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CN	Core Network
CT	Core Network and Terminals
CU	Centralized Unit
DU	Distributed Unit
ENI	Experimental Networked Intelligence
ESO	European Standards Organisation
ETI	Emerging Technology Initiative
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GSMA	Groupe Speciale Mobile Association
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IMT	International Mobile Telecommunications
IoT	Internet of Things
ISG	Industry Specification Group
ITANA	InTent Aware Network Autonomicity
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ITU-R	International Telecommunication Union - Radiocommunication Sector
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTE	Long-Term Evolution
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MWC	Mobile World Congress
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks
NFV	Network Functions Virtualisation
Near-RT RIC	Near Real-time RIC
Non-RT RIC	Non-Real-time RIC
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OODA	Observe-Orient-Decide-Act
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RU	Radio Unit
SA	Service and System Aspects
SG	Study Group
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SoTA	State of the Art
STF	Specialist Task Force

TC	Technical Committee
TCSEM	Technical Community on Semantic Computing
TN	Transport Node
TR	Technical Report
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TS	Technical Specification
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WRC	World Radiocommunication Conferences
WWRF	Wireless World Research Forum
ZSM	Zero Touch Network and Service Management

1 Introduction

6G-GOALS is poised to revolutionize the landscape of standardized Radio Access Network (RAN) specifications, prioritizing the integration of semantic and goal-oriented communication principles. Departing from traditional wireless network frameworks, this ground-breaking project will establish a new standardisation paradigm for 6G, transcending the current emphasis on centralized processing and rigid functional splits. Central to 6G-GOALS' approach is the facilitation of RAN intelligence and automation, fostering intelligent, context-aware, and personalized communication among devices and users. Leveraging advanced semantic technologies, machine learning, and AI, the project aims to distil the data that are strictly relevant to conveying the semantic meaning intended by the source and/or expected by the destination, or to fulfilling a predefined goal.

Beyond technical innovations, 6G-GOALS is poised to influence regulatory environments governing 6G networks. Through advocacy for regulation and policies enabling flexible end-to-end utilisation and sharing of radio network resource, the consortium aims to foster a more collaborative approach to 6G standardisation. Vigilant participation in standardisation bodies ensures that 6G-GOALS' innovations permeate the broader industry, impacting regulatory bodies such as ETSI and 3GPP.

Envisioning a future characterized by AI-based and semantic-assisted wireless networks, 6G-GOALS anticipates influencing discussions and contributions in 3GPP Release-19 and beyond. The project is committed to embracing open architectures, contributing to O-RAN standardisation, and enhancing industry partnerships to drive the evolution of wireless networks.

The success of 6G-GOALS hinges on its ability to deliver more intelligent, context-aware, and personalized communication experiences. This demands a strong focus on advancing semantic technologies and evolving Open RAN standards toward a distributed, flexible model. Semantic communications, as envisioned by 6G-GOALS, promises to reshape interactions with technology and between individuals, catalysing a transformative era for 6G networks.

This deliverable is a public document of the 6G-GOALS project, prepared as part of the Work Package (WP) 7 "Dissemination, exploitation, and standardisation" and focuses mainly on Task 7.3 "Standardisation". Deliverable 7.2 aims to develop a detailed dissemination and standardisation plan. It also involves identifying European and national initiatives that are relevant for the project and exploring opportunities for collaborative partnerships to maximize benefits.

Section 2 comes up with a description of the dissemination and communication plan.

Section 3 focuses on the standardisation plan, and it presents a list of standardisation bodies and associations relevant to 6G-GOALS, describing those that should be monitored and where the strongest impact can be achieved.

Section 4 describes the SNS Joint Undertaking framework 6G-GOALS is a part of, highlighting areas where the highest interaction can be achieved and defining contact points that can grant a proper level of collaboration with the other projects and 6G-IA working groups.

Section 5 concludes the document, summarizing its content and providing some general information on deliverables that will be subsequently published within WP7.

2 Dissemination Plan

6G-GOALS dissemination plan, more thoroughly discussed in Deliverable D7.1 [1], details the approaches and channels to effectively raise awareness and understanding of the project's outcomes among the wider public and specific target audience. Through the implementation of this strategy, the utilisation and reception of the research insights and findings generated throughout the duration of the 6G-GOALS project will be amplified. 6G-GOALS will leverage the ongoing

worldwide research efforts that form the core foundations of the project, namely semantic and goal-oriented communications through the integration of ML techniques, and actively engage in the subsequent five initiatives:

- 1) The IEEE Technical Community on Semantic Computing (TCSEM) is a community that was founded in 2010 with the objective of fostering research and advancements in the field of Semantic Computing, as well as developing standards. Furthermore, TCSEM intends to engage in partnerships and collaborations with other organisations and groups that are involved in Semantic Computing;
- 2) The IEEE Machine Learning for Communications Emerging Technology Initiative (ETI) provides an opportunity for 6G-GOALS to establish connections with other ETIs, thereby expanding the influence of Semantic Communication and ML in future 6G advancements. As part of this collaboration, 6G-GOALS will contribute valuable datasets and publications;
- 3) The IEEE Communication Society - Large Generative AI Models in Telecom (GenAINet) Emerging Technology Initiative. The aim of this initiative is to create a dynamic platform of research and innovation for academics, researchers, and industry leaders to advance the research on large generative AI in Telecom, which is highly connected with the principles of semantic communications. One of the Co-I of the 6G-GOALS project, Prof. Gunduz from ICL is a founding member and a Vice-Chair of this initiative. 6G-GOALS, through its participation in this initiative, will drive the research and technology principles on how foundational models can be used in future communication networks.
- 4) ITU-R WP5D works towards defining the vision and technologies for the network of 2030 and beyond. More specifically ITU-R is currently developing technical reports on Future Technology Trends, IMT-2030 Vision, and Above 100 GHz. Future opportunities for dissemination to ITU-R reports on 6G topics as well as influence future regulation actions, e.g., as part of the world radio conferences 2023 and 2027, will be pursued by the 6G-GOALS project;
- 5) The Wireless World Research Forum (WWRF) holds significant influence as a forum dedicated to fostering new ideas. WWRF convenes two meetings annually and produces "Outlooks" in the form of white papers, providing avenues for disseminating groundbreaking visions. The 6G-GOALS consortium will actively explore numerous opportunities for dissemination and contributions on diverse wireless subjects through collaboration with WWRF.

A key aim is to ensure the widespread dissemination and utilisation of the project's technical achievements and experimental findings within the scientific community. The project's preliminary, intermediate, and final outcomes will be continuously shared through the presentation of articles and research papers at various national and international conferences and workshops. With the expertise of its research partners, 6G-GOALS is committed to publishing and contributing to esteemed peer-reviewed scientific journals and conferences. To further strengthen the dissemination strategy, the project website will facilitate broad open access publishing and self-archiving. Given the abundance of conferences and journals, the coordinator and technical manager will exercise discretion in selecting the most suitable conferences to attend while prioritizing the publication quality. In addition, at least one specialized sessions and related events at significant conferences will be organized, delivering invited educational talks at universities, research institutes, and public academic and educational events. These initiatives aim to disseminate the research outcomes to the academic, educational, and research community. Moreover, the 6G-GOALS project outcomes will be utilized in subsequent research beyond the project's conclusion, including national/international collaborative projects, industrial research projects, and PhD dissertations.

3 Standardisation and Industrial Associations

In the rapidly evolving landscape of mobile telecommunications, standardisation plays a pivotal role in ensuring interoperability, fostering innovation, and driving the widespread adoption of new technologies. For the 6G-GOALS project, engaging with standardisation bodies and industrial associations is crucial to influencing the development of future 6G standards, particularly in the areas of AI-enabled learning and semantic communication networks.

This section outlines the strategic approach of 6G-GOALS towards standardisation, detailing the project's comprehensive plan to observe, derive, identify, and recommend standards based on its innovative research and findings. By actively collaborating with key industry stakeholders, 6G-GOALS aims to contribute to the development of the next generation of mobile network standards, ensuring that the advancements in semantic communications and AI technologies are integrated into the global telecommunications framework.

3.1 Standardisation Plan

One of the key objectives of 6G-GOALS is to ensure that the fundamental experience built through research and pre-deployment activities inside the consortium can be exploited to drive the development of relevant standards, and to enrich the discussion ongoing inside the main industry associations related to the evolution of mobile technologies towards 6G.

Figure 3-1 Standardisation plan Gantt chart

To reach the maximum impact on standardisation and relevant bodies 6G-GOALS has defined a four-step strategy (see Figure 3-1):

- **Observation of available standards.** In the first phase of the project, a comprehensive list of relevant entities, standardisation bodies, and associations will be identified and monitored. All stakeholders involved in the definition of 6G will be monitored, including public authorities. This step is already started, and its first results are covered in this deliverable, providing an extensive overview of the current landscape and identifying key players in the standardisation process.
- **Deriving required standards from 6G-GOALS use cases.** Based on the semantic use cases of 6G-GOALS, the most important input and features of standards and associations will be identified and used in 6G-GOALS. This phase will be completed after the

release of Deliverable D2.1, which will detail the specific use cases and requirements, allowing for a targeted approach to standard development.

- **Identification of gaps.** Through the experience derived from the project, missing elements or unclear information in existing standards will be identified, and potential solutions will be proposed to fill in the identified gaps. This continuous assessment will ensure that 6G-GOALS can effectively address and enhance the current standards landscape, making it more robust and comprehensive.
- **Recommendation to standardisation organisations.** Findings and results from the 6G-GOALS consortium will be used to recommend standardisation activities and development roadmaps. Furthermore, 6G-GOALS will report to consortia that represent stakeholders involved in the deployment of next-generation mobile networks, pushing to ensure that the project's innovations are adopted and integrated into future standards.

The following section reports the outcome of the first step of this strategy; it presents an overview of the main bodies dealing with the evolution of mobile technologies, highlighting the main activities relevant to 6G-GOALS carried out in these entities and keeping track of recent and upcoming studies and results that should be monitored during the project's life span.

3.2 Standards and Associations relevant for 6G-GOALS

The following tables, Table 3-1 and Table 3-2, summarize respectively the standard bodies and industrial associations that are considered relevant for 6G-GOALS. Tables include a brief description of the entity, its mission, which working groups or activities are particularly relevant for the 6G-GOALS project, and an indication of recent or upcoming results produced by the standard or associations that the 6G-GOALS partners should be aware of.

Additionally, Sections 3.2.1, 3.2.2 and 3.2.3 provide further details on the three standard bodies that are deemed more important for the development of 6G-GOALS activities, namely 3GPP, ORAN, and ETSI.

Table 3-1 Standard Bodies relevant for 6G-GOALS

3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)	
Mission	3GPP [3] covers cellular telecommunications network technologies, including radio access, the core network, UEs and service capabilities, thus providing complete end to end system specifications for a mobile network from 2G to 5G advanced and upcoming 6G.
Working groups and activities relevant to 6G-GOALS	Activities carried out by 3GPP's RAN1 and RAN2 working groups are strongly linked with the 6G-GOALS project, with RAN1 focusing on the physical layer and RAN2 on radio network signaling. RAN3's work on functional splits within C-RAN architectures supports efficient edge data processing, which is also important for the definition of the envisioned semantic intelligent controller. SA2's involvement in system architecture is key to incorporating scalable semantic processing into mobile networks. Meanwhile, SA5's focus on network management could significantly advance automated operations using semantic technologies, which can deliver intelligent network management and operational efficiency.
Recent & upcoming results	The next significant steps in the 3GPP roadmap focus on continuing the development of 5G Advanced under Release 19 and setting the stage for 6G, which will be explored more extensively in Release 20 and beyond. Release 19, which follows the enhancements introduced in Release 18, aims to boost network performance and to accommodate new

	applications and use cases, integrating advanced AI/ML capabilities, which will be a fundamental enabler for the integration of semantics communication. Further details are provided in Section 3.2.1.
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O-RAN Alliance (O-RAN)	
Mission	O-RAN ALLIANCE [4] is a world-wide community of mobile operators, vendors, and research & academic institutions operating in the Radio Access Network (RAN) industry. O-RAN ALLIANCE’s mission is to reshape the RAN industry towards more intelligent, open, virtualized and fully interoperable mobile networks. O-RAN specifications enable a more competitive and vibrant RAN supplier ecosystem with faster innovation to improve user experience.
Working groups and activities relevant to 6G-GOALS	The activities carried out by O-RAN ALLIANCE’s WPs 1-4 are closely related to the 6G-GOALS project. WG1 has the overall responsibility for the O-RAN Use Cases and Overall Architecture. The WG2 works on Non-Real-time RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC) and A1 Interface, which aims to support Non-RT intelligent radio resource management, policy optimisation in RAN, and providing AI/ML models to Near-RT RIC. This is important for deploying intelligent semantic modules in RIC. WG3 focus on defining Near-RT RIC and E2 Interface, so as to enable near-real-time control and optimisation of RAN elements and resources. WP4’s goal is to specify the open fronthaul interface between O-DU/SMO and O-RU, and the cooperative transport interface between O-DU and TN. These activities could potentially support and enable the effective processing of semantic information within O-RAN. Further details are available in Section 3.2.2.
Recent & upcoming results	<p>ORAN has recently released different specifications that are relevant for 6G-GOALS [5]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Cases Analysis Report and Detailed Specifications (v13.00) - (WG1) • RAN Non-RT RIC Architecture (v5.00) - (WG2) • RAN Non-RT RIC & A1 interface: Use Cases and Requirements v9.00 - (WG2) • RAN R1 interface: General Aspects and Principles v7.00 - (WG2) • RAN Control, User and Synchronisation Plane Specification (v14.00) - (WG4) <p>The O-RAN ALLIANCE has launched the Certification and Badging Program, which targets to accelerate the adoption of open and intelligent Radio Access Networks (RAN) through building confidence in O-RAN products and solutions world-wide.</p>

European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)

<p>Mission</p>	<p>ETSI [2] is a European Standards Organisation (ESO). It is the recognized regional standards body dealing with telecommunications, broadcasting and other electronic communications networks and services. It supports European regulations and legislation through the creation of Harmonized European Standards.</p>
<p>Working groups and activities relevant to 6G-GOALS</p>	<p>ETSI is structured into various Technical Committees (TCs) and Industry Specification Groups (ISGs). TCs develop standards for a wide range of technologies, from radio equipment and systems to digital broadcasting and cybersecurity. ISGs address specific technical areas or market sectors that require rapid development of specifications outside the usual standards development process. ISGs are more flexible than TCs and can be created quickly in response to market needs, bringing together industry players to collaborate on specific topics.</p> <p>Example of relevant Industry Specification Groups for 6G-GOALS are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Experimental networked intelligence (ENI)” develops standards that use AI mechanisms to assist in the management and orchestration of the network. The group’s work focuses on improving the operator experience, using closed-loop AI mechanisms based on context-aware, metadata-driven policies. This enables the ENI system to recognize and incorporate new and changed knowledge, and hence make actionable decisions. • “Zero touch network and Service Management (ZSM)” devoted to full end-to-end automation of network and service management to enable largely autonomous networks driven by high-level policies and rules. ZSM targets the characterisation of self-configurable, self-monitored, self-healing and self-optimizing networks. <p>More details are provided in Section 3.2.3.</p>
<p>Recent & upcoming results</p>	<p>ETSI GR ZSM 009-3 V1.1.1 recommends the use of semantic knowledge representation (e.g., ontology graphs) within the ZSM closed loops.</p> <p>ETSI GR ZSM 011 V1.1.1 highlights how well-defined information models for intent-driven autonomous networks need to involve the semantic representation of instructions for network components of the definition of network operations, so that the sender and receiver of intents agree in their interpretation (independently from them being humans or machines).</p> <p>ETSI ENI group has defined the system architecture ontologies, semantics and intent description language as recommended works planned in next releases.</p> <p>ENI control loops are based on extensions to the OODA (Observe-Orient-Decide-Act) architecture. These extensions add AI mechanisms (e.g., learning and reasoning), along with formal semantics and cognition, to the basic structure of an OODA control loop.</p> <p>ETSI ENI group has also introduced a semantic analyser in the InTent Aware Network Autonomicity architecture (ITANA) as a Functional Block and semantic bus for using intent with the ENI System Architecture. As described in the ETSI ETSI GR ENI 008 document, “Purpose is to enable Intent Policy semantically augmented as part of the system architecture and capability to support intent policies.”</p>

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International Telecommunication Union - Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R)	
Mission	The International Telecommunication Union - Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) [6] manages and coordinates the global use of the radio-frequency spectrum. Its mission is to ensure efficient, equitable, and interference-free use of the radio spectrum for various services, promoting global radiocommunication service development.
Working groups and activities relevant to 6G-GOALS	ITU-R operates through several Study Groups (SGs) and Working Parties (WPs) that focus on different aspects of radiocommunications. Study Group 5 (SG 5), particularly Working Party 5D (WP 5D), has the responsibility to establish Recommendations on IMT Systems, thus having a crucial role for the definition of future technologies, integrating semantic communication capabilities. Additionally, Study Group 3 (SG 3) and Working Party 3K (WP 3K) on Point-to-Area Propagation develop propagation models vital for network design, ensuring reliable and efficient communication.
Recent & upcoming results	ITU-R has developed a complete set of Recommendations and reports on IMT-2020 (5G), including spectrum aspects and performance requirements, and allocated new frequency bands for IMT systems. Looking ahead, ITU-R WP5D has already defined the framework and overall objectives for IMT-2030, which will set the scene for 6G technologies. ITU-R WP5D will then define the technical requirements and evaluation criteria for IMT-2030 and it will subsequently coordinate the evaluation of candidate radio interface technologies developed by external organisations (such as 3GPP) with the objective to develop a Recommendation on IMT-2030 radio interface specifications by year 2030. The World Radiocommunication Conference 2023 (WRC-23) addressed additional spectrum needs for IMT, considering 6G requirements. Furthermore, ongoing studies aim to enhance propagation models to support high-frequency bands essential for 6G.

Table 3-2 Industrial Association relevant for 6G-GOALS

Groupe Speciale Mobile Association (GSMA)	
Mission	GSMA [7] represents the interests of mobile operators worldwide, bringing together 664 operators as full GSMA members and more than 400 companies in the broader mobile ecosystem, including also handset and device makers, software companies, equipment providers and internet companies, as well as organisations in adjacent industry sectors [8]. The GSMA represents its members via industry programmes, working groups and industry advocacy initiatives. The GSMA also produces the Mobile World Congress (MWC) events held annually in Barcelona, Los Angeles, and Shanghai.
Working groups and activities relevant to 6G-GOALS	GSMA operates through various communities focused on advancing mobile technology and services. The GSMA 5G Futures Community is a significant initiative relevant to 6G-GOALS. This community brings together leading operators and industry players to promote the adoption

	<p>and evolution of 5G and 5G-Advanced technologies, exploring new business models and technical advancements essential for the transition to 6G. Additionally, the GSMA AI for Impact initiative explores the integration of artificial intelligence in mobile networks, aligning with 6G-GOALS' objectives to leverage AI for enhanced network performance and semantic communication. Another relevant initiative is the GSMA Internet of Things (IoT) Community, which helps operators accelerate the delivery of new connected devices and services in the IoT sector. This community focuses on industry collaboration, appropriate regulation, optimizing networks, and developing key enablers to support the growth of IoT, which is critical for the future development of 6G networks and semantic communication.</p>
<p>Recent & upcoming results</p>	<p>Recently, GSMA has promoted global 5G deployment through initiatives such as the 5G Innovation Fund, supporting the development and commercialisation of 5G technologies. The GSMA 5G Futures Community has driven innovation and verification of key 5.5G technologies and scenarios, preparing the industry for the next evolution in mobile networks. The GSMA IoT Community has also played a pivotal role in advancing IoT technologies, crucial for integrating various IoT applications into future 6G networks.</p> <p>Upcoming efforts include defining 6G roadmap, requirements, and use cases, with a focus on integrating AI, and potentially semantic and goal-oriented communication capabilities to enhance network efficiency and user experiences. The GSMA's Mobile World Congress (MWC) events in Barcelona continue to be key platforms for showcasing innovations and shaping the future of mobile communications, including the transition to 6G.</p>

<p>Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGMN) Alliance</p>	
<p>Mission</p>	<p>The Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGMN) Alliance [9] is dedicated to ensuring the successful commercialisation of future mobile broadband networks and services. Its mission is to provide a coherent vision for the evolution of mobile networks, fostering collaboration among operators, vendors, and research institutions to drive the development of innovative, high-performance mobile broadband technologies.</p>
<p>Working groups and activities relevant to 6G-GOALS</p>	<p>NGMN operates through various projects and task forces focusing on different aspects of mobile network development. NGMN addresses key aspects of 5G and its evolution towards 6G, including end-to-end architecture, security, spectrum, and operational efficiency. NGMN's Strategic Focus Topics are continuously adapted to meet these priorities. For 2024 and beyond, NGMN focuses on three major areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Route to Disaggregation with a Focus on the E2E Operating Model initiative explores the separation of network components, enabling more flexible, efficient, and scalable network architectures. This modular approach supports innovation and adaptability, essential for integrating semantic communication technologies in 6G, where network functions can be dynamically adjusted based on semantic data analysis. • The Green Future Networks / Sustainability initiative promotes sustainable and energy-efficient mobile network solutions.

	<p>This focus on reducing energy consumption and improving efficiency is crucial for the large-scale deployment of semantic communication systems, which require processing and transmitting vast amounts of data in an environmentally friendly manner.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The 6G project provides early and timely direction for global 6G activities. By focusing on future societal needs and technological trends, this project helps shape the development of 6G standards. Semantic communication, which relies on AI and context-aware data handling, is a key area of interest. This project's insights into the drivers and requirements for 6G are directly relevant to advancing semantic communication technologies.
<p>Recent & upcoming results</p>	<p>Recently, NGMN has concentrated on the practical deployment and optimisation of 5G networks, publishing comprehensive white papers and guidelines on 5G deployment. These documents are essential for operators and vendors working on 5G and future 6G technologies. In the 6G focus area, NGMN has published significant deliverables: "6G Drivers and Vision" [17], "6G Use Cases and Analysis" [18], and "6G Requirements and Design Considerations" [19]. These documents outline the key drivers, use cases, and technical requirements for 6G networks, providing a foundation for developing 6G standards. Future efforts will continue to explore advanced use cases and guide the development of next-generation network technologies, ensuring they align with global demands and sustainability goals.</p>

<p>6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA)</p>	
<p>Mission</p>	<p>The 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) [10] is the voice of European industry and research for next-generation networks and services. Its primary objective is to contribute to Europe's leadership in 5G, 5G evolution, and SNS/6G research. The 6G-IA represents the private sector in both the 5G Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) and the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU), fostering collaboration among telecom operators, manufacturers, research institutes, universities, SMEs, and ICT associations.</p>
<p>Working groups and activities relevant to 6G-GOALS</p>	<p>The 6G-IA carries out a wide range of activities in strategic areas including standardisation, frequency spectrum management, R&D projects, and technology skills development. It collaborates with key vertical industry sectors for the development of trials and international cooperation. For 6G-GOALS, the 6G-IA's focus on advanced R&D projects and international collaboration is particularly relevant as these activities support the integration and advancement of semantic communication technologies. The association's work on standardisation and spectrum management also ensures that future 6G networks can efficiently handle the high data volumes and sophisticated processing required for semantic communications.</p>
<p>Recent & upcoming results</p>	<p>Recently, 6G-IA has produced several key deliverables relevant to the 6G-GOALS project. The "Open Networks and Services" whitepaper [13] explores the opportunities of open ICT platforms, essential for disaggregated network deployment and efficient operation. The "Open RAN and</p>

6G Future Networks Development" whitepaper [14] discusses new network architectures for 6G, focusing on flexibility and optimisation of network functions. Additionally, the "EU-US Beyond 5G/6G Roadmap" [15] and "Key Strategies for 6G Smart Networks and Services" [16] provide strategic reflections and recommendations for future 6G networks, addressing collaboration and development priorities.

Upcoming activities include further exploration of advanced use cases, fostering international cooperation, and aligning global efforts in 6G research and development. As further discussed in Section 4.1, the SNS JU, which 6G IA is connected to, has adopted its 2024 Research & Innovation Work Programme, which earmarks €129 million for collaborative projects to advance 6G systems and prepare for standardisation activities. This program includes streams focused on revolutionary technology advancements, system enablers, and large-scale trials with verticals.

3.2.1 3GPP

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) [3] was established in December 1998 as a collaborative project to develop globally applicable standards for mobile systems. Initially focused on the evolution of GSM and related 3G technologies, 3GPP has since broadened its scope to include LTE (4G) and, most recently, 5G technologies. The objective of 3GPP is to produce Technical Specifications (TS) and Technical Reports (TR) for mobile telecommunications, ensuring interoperability and seamless global connectivity.

Organisation and Working Groups

3GPP is organized into three main Technical Specification Groups (TSGs), each comprising several Working Groups (WGs) responsible for different aspects of mobile communications:

1. Radio Access Network (RAN)

- RAN1: Focuses on the physical layer of the radio interface, including aspects like coding, modulation, and multiple access.
- RAN2: Deals with the radio interface architecture and protocols, including layer 2 protocols and Radio Resource Control (RRC).
- RAN3: Concentrates on the radio access network architecture and interfaces, including the interfaces between the RAN and the core network.
- RAN4: Works on the radio performance and protocol aspects, including requirements for base stations and user equipment.
- RAN5: Involved in mobile terminal conformance testing and validation of the radio aspects.

2. Core Network and Terminals (CT)

- CT1: Focuses on user equipment to Core Network protocols.
- CT3: Deals with the interworking with external networks & policy and charging control.
- CT4: Focuses on core network protocols.
- CT6: Deals with smart card application aspects.

3. Service and System Aspects (SA)

- SA1: Is responsible for the overall service requirements.
- SA2: Focuses on the system and service architecture, including network interfaces and end-to-end service performance.
- SA3: Handles security and privacy aspects.
- SA4: Works on codecs, multimedia, and media handling.
- SA5: Focuses on network management and orchestration.
- SA6: Responsible for mission-critical applications and services.

Figure 3-2 3GPP release 18-19 timeline.

3GPP follows a structured roadmap for its releases (see Figure 3-2), each introducing new features and enhancements. For the development towards 6G, 3GPP has recently agreed the following, as highlighted in Figure 3-3:

- Release 18 (2022-2024): Focuses on further enhancements to 5G, including improvements in AI/ML integration, network automation, and support for new use cases.
- Release 19 (2024-2025): Will introduce, further enhancements on AI-driven network management, and on energy efficiency, A-IoT and initial studies on JSAC.
- Release 20 (2025-2027): Planned to define feasibility studies on 6G standards, incorporating further integration of AI across network layers, and new service architectures, which could provide support for semantic communications.
- Release 21: timeline to be decided no later than June 2026, expected to start to specify 6G standard.

The continuous development in these releases will pave the way for fully realized 6G networks, where semantic communication can play an important role in achieving improved levels of efficiency, intelligence, and user-centric performance.

6G timeline agreed in March 2024

Figure 3-3 6G timeline currently agreed in 3GPP.

In that sense, activities carried on 3GPP working groups may set the stage for the development of semantic communications and can benefit from the research and outcomes of the 6G-GOALS project. Semantic communication is poised to revolutionize mobile networks by enabling intelligent, context-aware, and goal-oriented data exchange, thus potentially having a huge impact on evolving the current mobile standard. In particular:

- **RAN1 and RAN2:** These groups' work on the physical layer and radio protocols is essential for implementing semantic communication at the radio interface level. Techniques like semantic coding and modulation can enhance spectral efficiency and reduce latency.
- **RAN3:** As this group focuses on the RAN architecture, it plays a crucial role in integrating semantic processing capabilities into the RAN, enabling more efficient data handling and transmission.
- **SA2:** This group's work on system architecture is vital for incorporating semantic-aware functionalities across the network, ensuring that data is processed and transmitted based on its semantic relevance.
- **SA5:** Network management and orchestration can benefit significantly from semantic technologies, enabling more intelligent and automated network operations.
- **SA6:** Semantic and goal-oriented communication is highly relevant to the work of SA6, as these technologies can significantly enhance the performance and reliability of mission-critical applications, providing more context-aware data transmission, ensuring that critical information is prioritized and delivered with minimal delay, and applying more robust error correction and redundancy techniques to mission-critical information, thus enhancing reliability.

The 6G-GOALS project aims to study solutions that can impact several aspects of 3GPP standards:

- **Enhanced AI/ML Integration:** By introducing advanced AI and ML techniques for semantic data processing, 6G-GOALS can contribute to the development of more intelligent network management and data transmission protocols.

- **New KPIs and Metrics:** The project can help define new Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that focus on the semantic value of data, rather than traditional metrics like throughput and latency.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Semantic communication techniques can significantly reduce the amount of data transmitted, leading to lower energy consumption and more sustainable network operations.

By ensuring that semantic communication techniques are compatible with existing and upcoming 3GPP standards, 6G-GOALS can facilitate a smooth transition for the integration of the novel concept of semantic and goal-oriented communication in future 6G networks.

3.2.2 O-RAN

The O-RAN Alliance (Open Radio Access Network Alliance) [4] is a global coalition comprising mobile network operators, vendors, and research institutions. Its core objective is to advance the development of open, intelligent, and interoperable RAN technologies. Since its establishment the O-RAN effort expanded to include over 300 organisations, encompassing major operators and vendors including key 6G-GOALS partners like NEC and TIM. The O-RAN architecture represents a novel paradigm in mobile network construction, aiming to enhance flexibility, interoperability, and innovation. It facilitates multi-vendor deployments, cost reduction, and improved network performance through several key features:

- **Open Interfaces:** O-RAN architecture establishes open and standardized interfaces between RAN components like the Radio Unit (RU), Distributed Unit (DU), and Centralized Unit (CU), fostering multivendor interoperability and competitiveness.
- **Functional Split:** This architecture implements a functional split among the RU, DU, and CU, with each unit handling specific tasks such as radio frequency processing, real-time data management, and non-real-time processing and control. This modular design supports flexible deployment and scalability.
- **RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC):** The RIC integrates AI and machine learning capabilities into the network, leveraging real-time RAN data to make intelligent decisions and automate functions, thereby enhancing efficiency and reducing operational costs.
- **Cloud-Native Platforms:** O-RAN promotes the adoption of cloud-native platforms for RAN components, enabling a more agile and scalable network infrastructure. This approach supports modern software development principles like containerisation and microservices, simplifying deployment, management, and upgrades.
- **Open-Source Software:** The O-RAN Alliance advocates for the development of open-source software and reference designs, fostering innovation and collaboration in the RAN ecosystem. Lowering entry barriers for new vendors and accelerating feature development, open-source drives progress and diversity in the industry.

Therefore, the O-RAN architecture represents a paradigm shift in mobile network design, promoting open interfaces, functional split, intelligent control, cloud-native platforms, and open-source software to create a more flexible, interoperable, and innovative RAN ecosystem. Consequently, O-RAN represents a perfect arena for 6G-GOALS to push its technology innovations in the context of the O-RAN interoperability and novel solutions for core network interconnectivity based on semantic and context awareness.

As the O-RAN Alliance progresses, its focus remains on refining specifications, encouraging open-source contributions, and promoting the widespread adoption of open RAN technologies across the telecommunications industry. Unlike 3GPP, the Alliance's planning process is more organic, with features agreed upon for specific phases but subject to ongoing refinement. While

the Alliance is currently discussing a shift towards a more structured approach similar to 3GPP, with advanced feature announcements and adherence to a predefined plan, this transition is expected to occur during the lifespan of 6G-GOALS. Within the Alliance, work is organized through various working groups (WGs) and task forces, each dedicated to different aspects of RAN development, including architecture, software, interfaces, and testing. Some of the key WGs and their focus areas are:

- **WG1 (Use Cases and Architecture):** Defines use cases, requirements, and O-RAN system architecture, focusing on system decomposition, interface specifications, and functional splits. 6G-GOALS will propose a semantic enhanced RICs to assist Network Functions with compute-aware radio scheduling procedures, and coordinate interaction with core network functionalities.
- **WG2 (Non-RT RIC and A1 Interface):** Develops and standardizes non-real-time RIC and A1 interface for higher-layer functions, policy management, and optimisation. 6G-GOALS can impact WG2 with demonstrations of distributed sensing exploiting multi-modal data fusion, semantic communication, and generative AI, proposing extensions to make data management and AI/ML pipelines more agile and less energy demanding.
- **WG3 (Near-RT RIC and E2 Interface):** Standardizes near-real-time RIC and E2 interface for real-time control and optimisation, like radio resource management and interference management. 6G-GOALS can impact WG3 with demonstrations of Near-RT RIC solutions and proposing extensions to enable semantic-aware Near-RT RIC reconfiguration and its seamless integration with the proposed S-RIC.
- **WG4 (Open Fronthaul Interfaces):** Develops open fronthaul interfaces for RU-DU connections in O-RAN systems, promoting interoperability and competition. 6G-GOALS may impact WG4 with smart fronthaul solutions that may help reduce the energy consumption of virtualized RAN systems by exploiting semantic communication approaches.

3.2.3 ETSI

The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) [2] is a leading standardisation organisation established in 1988, tasked with developing globally applicable standards for Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), including fixed, mobile, radio, broadcast, and internet technologies. ETSI's mission is to produce high-quality standards that enable global interoperability and drive technological innovation, ensuring that Europe remains at the forefront of ICT development.

As previously discussed, ETSI is organized into various Technical Committees (TCs) and Industry Specification Groups (ISGs), each focused on specific aspects of ICT. These groups bring together industry stakeholders, including manufacturers, network operators, service providers, research institutions, and regulatory authorities, to develop and maintain standards that meet market needs. Beside the Zero touch network and Service Management (ZSM) and Experimental Networked Intelligence (ENI) groups (see Table 3-1), other working groups relevant to the development of semantic communications in 6G-GOALS include:

- **ETSI Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC):** ETSI MEC aims to create an open environment for efficient and agile deployment of applications at the network edge. This is crucial for reducing latency and improving service delivery for real-time applications. Semantic communications require low-latency processing, which MEC facilitates by enabling computation closer to the end-users. By integrating semantic data processing at the edge, MEC can significantly enhance the responsiveness and efficiency of 6G networks.
- **ETSI Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV):** ETSI NFV focuses on virtualizing network functions to allow network operators to deploy services dynamically without the

need for dedicated hardware. The flexibility provided by NFV is essential for implementing semantic-aware network functions that can be dynamically instantiated and scaled based on semantic data analysis and AI-driven insights.

The 6G-GOALS project is set to impact ETSI activities through:

- **Advanced AI/ML Integration:** By introducing sophisticated AI and ML techniques for semantic data processing, 6G-GOALS can contribute to developing smarter, more efficient network functions and management protocols.
- **Semantic-aware Network Functions:** The project can help define new standards for semantic-aware network functions, ensuring that data is processed and transmitted based on its semantic value, which can enhance service quality and efficiency.
- **Enhanced Automation:** Semantic communication can significantly advance the goals of initiatives like ZSM and ENI, enabling more intelligent and automated network operations.

In terms of timing, ETSI recognizes that the 3GPP 6G work plan is expected to begin at the end of 2025 (e.g., Release 20). Therefore, it is essential for ETSI to accumulate sufficient knowledge to generate impact and shape the standardisation work in 3GPP in the next 3 to 5 years in mid-term, and 5-10 years in long-term (see [11]).

These activities will pave the way for fully realized 6G networks, where semantic communication and AI can be integral to achieving higher levels of efficiency, intelligence, and user-centric performance.

To ensure a better impact of 6G-GOALS in ETSI, the project will advocate for the creation of a specific Industry Specification Group (ISG) on semantics and goal-oriented communication, or for the inclusion of this topic within one of the current ISGs. This approach will capitalize on the existing workforce, organisational structure, and the extensive network of partners already collaborating efficiently and effectively.

4 Interactions with other 6G-SNS JU initiatives

In the context of 6G Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) [12], 6G-GOALS fully embraces the technological objectives and the vision of future mobile networks and services that characterise the European Commission's H2020 and Horizon Europe programmes. Thus, Section 4.1 briefly introduces the SNS JU initiative with the aim of outlining the framework in which the project is evolving. 6G-GOALS's targeted technological advancements, although ambitious and exploring potentially disruptive innovations, will rely on the expertise that the consortium partners have acquired from the participation in previously or still active projects within such programmes. For 6G-GOALS, it is key to have a mature vision on the SoTA of telecommunication technologies and on the directions that other leading activities at a continental level are taking in this domain. With this in mind, Sections 4.2 and 4.3 provide a selection of European and national projects respectively, whose results and achievements would be useful inputs for 6G-GOALS's work. Furthermore, these sections specify whether and which partners of the 6G-GOALS consortium have had an active role in other projects and/or initiatives, indicating how their work can be leveraged by 6G-GOALS or in which way 6G-GOALS's results will differ from them.

4.1 The SNS-JU initiative

The 6G Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) is an ambitious initiative formed by the European Commission and the 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA). Launched in November 2021, its primary goal is to position Europe as a leader in next-generation connectivity by fostering research and innovation in 6G technologies. The

initiative focuses on maintaining Europe’s technological sovereignty, leading global 6G standards, and promoting sustainable network technologies.

SNS JU's strategic objectives encompass enhancing 5G deployment, pioneering 6G research, and building robust ecosystems that integrate academia, industry, and policy-makers. By accelerating the rollout of advanced 5G networks, leading global research initiatives, and creating an ecosystem of stakeholders, SNS JU aims to achieve significant technological advancements.

The initiative's key research and development areas include developing flexible, scalable, and secure network architectures, integrating artificial intelligence for autonomous network management, and promoting energy-efficient technologies to reduce future networks' carbon footprint. These efforts are complemented by industrial leadership, where partnerships with key industry players help translate research into practical applications. SNS JU also plays a pivotal role in global standardisation efforts, ensuring interoperability and widespread adoption of 6G technologies.

Funding for SNS JU involves a substantial €900 million EU contribution for 2021-2027, matched by equivalent industry contributions. The project operates through three main phases: Research and Development, Scaling Innovations, and Commercial Deployment, as Figure 4-1 shows.

Figure 4-1 SNS JU roadmap (source [12])

A variety of projects are supported under SNS JU, addressing critical aspects of 6G development. These include flagship projects focused on fundamental research and technological breakthroughs, thematic clusters tackling specific challenges like network security and AI integration, and open calls for proposals inviting participation from academia, industry, and SMEs. Looking ahead, SNS JU aims to advance pre-standardisation work, enhance cross-border collaboration, and promote innovation trials to test and refine 6G technologies in real-world settings. These efforts position SNS JU to lead the global transition to 6G, fostering innovation and ensuring sustainable and inclusive technological progress.

6G-GOALS is part of SNS JU Phase 2, specifically within Stream B “Wireless Communication Technologies and Signal Processing”. This stream focuses on conducting research to drive revolutionary advancements in technology, particularly in anticipation of the 6G era and revolutionary enhancements in IoT, devices, and software. Within the SNS JU Work Programme 2023 (WP2023), this stream aims to address low to medium Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), delivering innovative solutions geared towards real-world networks over an extended timeframe.

In this context, semantic communications represent a transformative shift in the design and implementation of communication networks, emphasizing the transmission of meaning rather than merely data. This approach aligns closely with the objectives of the SNS JU, which seeks to advance the next generation of communication networks, including 6G.

The SNS JU focuses on integrating advanced technologies such as AI and ML to optimize network operations, aiming for networks that are not only faster and more reliable but also intelligent and context-aware. Within this framework, semantic communications are pivotal as they promise to reduce the amount of data transmitted by focusing on the transmission of essential information, thereby improving efficiency, and reducing latency.

The integration of semantic communications within the SNS JU's framework through projects like 6G-GOALS will pave the way for the development of smarter, more sustainable, and highly efficient communication networks. These advancements will not only meet the stringent requirements of future applications but also set new standards for global communication technologies.

4.2 Projects relevant to 6G-GOALS

Table 4-1 provides a comparison of various projects, highlighting their objectives, contributions, and key differences relative to the 6G-GOALS initiative. The table includes projects, either currently ongoing or recently closed, that contribute to the advancement of 6G research, offering unique insights and technologies that are instrumental in shaping future wireless networks. By understanding the objectives and contributions of these projects, 6G-GOALS can leverage their findings to enhance semantic communication, improve network efficiency, and address emerging application requirements. The table outlines overlapping partners where applicable and elucidates the specific relevance and distinguishing features of each project in the context of 6G development.

Table 4-1 Related European projects

Project name & Overlapping partners (if any)	Objective / Relevance to 6G-GOALS & Key differences
<p>HEXA-X (CEA, TIM)</p>	<p>Objective: Hexa-X acknowledges the need to broaden the mobile network design approach, shifting from primarily performance-driven to encompass both performance and value considerations. In this context, "value" encompasses essential yet intangible human and societal requirements like sustainability, trust, and inclusivity. This evolution introduces a new set of evaluation criteria known as Key Value Indicators (KVIs), which are crucial for understanding, developing, and integrating into network designs for the transition to 6G.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: The Hexa-X project has established a well-defined roadmap and fostered innovations within the Beyond 5G (B5G) ecosystem. 6G-GOALS intends to capitalize on these achievements by leveraging them to identify and address application requirements, as well as the semantic aspects of information processing and transmission. This approach aims to enhance efficiency and minimize network traffic while maintaining comparable application performance and user experience.</p>

<p>HEXA-X-II (TIM)</p> <p>HEXA-X-II</p>	<p>Objective: Hexa-X-II endeavours to spearhead the advancement of end-to-end (E2E) system design and the formulation of enabling platforms for the upcoming generation (6G) of wireless networks. In this initiative, the focus is placed on placing humans at the core of future 6G network evolution, delineating use cases, services, and requirements that hold substantial societal value.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: Recognizing and comprehending the role of humans in shaping the future landscape of 6G systems is pivotal for the evolution of current mobile network scenarios. In this context, 6G-GOALS will actualize this notion by harnessing semantic communication to imbue networking entities with human-like capabilities, thereby facilitating more streamlined and productive interactions of the different network components.</p>
<p>6G-DISAC (CEA, TIM, NEC-EU)</p>	<p>Objective: The 6G-DISAC project aims to bring the integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) vision to life by adopting a holistic perspective with widely distributed intelligent infrastructure compatible with real-world integration constraints and future wireless network flexibility requirements. The project addresses both fundamental and practical challenges, such as tracking connected UEs and passive objects, performing ISAC with many distributed base stations, efficient distributed signal processing and machine learning for semantic ISAC, incorporating extremely large MIMO technologies and reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, and intelligent sensing activation. 6G-DISAC will focus on the distributed implementation of ISAC, unlocking real sensing applications and providing a multi-perspective view of networks in space and time for tangible communication gains. It will bridge theoretical approaches with operational and standards-compatible distributed joint communication and sensing.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: The architecture and algorithmic aspects devised within the DISAC project will be considered as inputs of WP2 and WP3 activities, and potentially extended to include semantic-oriented communication paradigm to reduce communication overhead and boost performances.</p>
<p>BeGREEN (NEC)</p>	<p>Objective: BeGREEN proposes a holistic approach to evolve radio networks that consider power consumption as a key factor, in addition to increasing traffic and services. Moreover, BeGREEN aims to integrate the ISAC concept into the O-RAN framework by devising data model and interfaces that allow to process low-level radio samples at the near Real-Time and Real-Time Radio Intelligent Controller (RICS).</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: 6G-GOALS objectives go beyond the development of a green wireless access architecture for communication, targeting instead a fully integrated semantic communication network.</p>

<p>5G-ERA (NEC)</p>	<p>Objective: 5G-ERA aims to provide an enhanced 5G experimentation facility and relevant Network Applications (NetApps) for 3rd party application developers by i) integrating operational processes of essential autonomous robotic capabilities, ii) exploiting intent-based networking paradigm to match end-to-end (E2E) resource optimisation with the autonomous operations, and iii) adopting Cloud native approach for the development of Network Services and functions.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: Like 6G-GOALS, the 5G-ERA project investigates the adoption of goal-oriented communication, with focus to improve the set-up and working performance of 5G-enabled robotics systems.</p>
<p>ADROIT 6G (CNIT, EUR)</p>	<p>Objective: The project's main objective is to develop a highly adaptive and intelligent communication system that can efficiently use network resources and adapt to changing network conditions in real-time, exploiting AI and ML techniques, such as deep learning and reinforcement learning.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: ADROIT 6G does not consider semantic-communication aspects when dealing with their adaptive and intelligent communication system</p>
<p>DETERMINISTIC 6G (None)</p>	<p>Objective: DETERMINISTIC 6G focuses on advancing the research and development of the next generation of wireless communication networks - 6G. The project focuses on addressing major challenges faced by the current wireless networks, such as network latency, reliability, and energy efficiency, by developing a deterministic communication framework.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences (WP3-WP6): The insights obtained by the real-life application of AI algorithms gained in DETERMINISTIC 6G will be fundamental to understand the application of AI at scale and will be applied in the evaluation sites of the project.</p>
<p>CENTRIC (AAU, CNIT)</p>	<p>Objective: CENTRIC project aims at developing a sustainable AI-native Air-Interface for 6G networks, with a goal to revolutionize wireless communication through user-centric design. The CENTRIC vision begins with a top-down, modular approach that starts with users' objectives and application-specific requirements.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: AI techniques developed in CENTRIC project are then employed to tailor-make waveforms, transceivers, signaling, protocols, and resource management procedures to support these requirements, resulting in what we refer to as the user-centric AI Air Interface (AI-AI).</p>
<p>COREnext (TIM)</p>	<p>Objective: COREnext is an EU-funded project aiming to revolutionize future mobile networks by developing a trustworthy-by-design computing platform specifically for B5G/6G. COREnext will offer efficient, scalable and virtualizable accelerators and thus answer the need for drastically enhancing the European capabilities and foundation regarding hardware, computing, and signal processing technologies for B5G and 6G infrastructures in the context of disaggregated, virtualized networks.</p>

	<p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: COREnext emphasizes a new computing architecture for base stations to advance B5G/6G capabilities with a strong focus on trustworthiness, energy efficiency, and supporting the EU economy, it complements 6G-GOALS, strengthening the hardware foundation over which 6G-GOALS can develop AI for intelligent network functionalities.</p>
<p>6G BRAINS (EUR)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: 5G BRAINS investigates the adoption of reinforcement learning techniques into radio light network for massive connections.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: The concepts of adaptable and self-learning AI-methods are central also in 6G-GOALS, which will leverage their outcome to achieve a more effective interaction between the service provider and the network.</p>
<p>5G CLARITY (None)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: 5G Clarity designs a system beyond 5G private Networks to address challenges in spectrum flexibility, delivery of critical services and autonomic network management using heterogeneous wireless access that integrates 5G, Wi-Fi, and LiFi technologies through novel AI-based autonomic networking.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: The spectrum flexibility introduced by the 5G-CLARITY project does not consider semantic communication for effective network control and management.</p>
<p>AI@EDGE (TIM, HPE-IT)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: AI@EDGE develops a connect-compute fabric, leveraging on the serverless paradigm, for creating and managing resilient, elastic, and secure end-to-end slices.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: The closed-loop network automation paradigm proposed by the AI@EDGE project will be modified and extended in 6G-GOALS to include adaptive semantic oriented communication schemes. Also, the experience gained from AI@EDGE's use case on Industrial IoT will be useful for the PoC of 6G-GOALS.</p>
<p>DAEMON (NEC)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: DAEMON develops and implements innovative and pragmatic approaches to Network Intelligence design that enables high performance, sustainable and extremely reliable zero-touch network systems.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: The architecture and algorithmic aspects devised within the DAEMON project will be considered as inputs of 6G-GOALS WP2 and WP3 activities, and potentially extended to include semantic-oriented communication paradigm to reduce communication overhead and boost performances.</p>
<p>LEXNET (CEA)</p>	<p>Main Outcomes: The main goal of LEXNET was to investigate methods, technologies and architectures to reduce the global population exposure to EMF induced by wireless networks.</p> <p>Relevance to Project & Key differences: 6G-GOALS will go further beyond LEXNET by employing EE and semantic compression methods to reduce the exposure index in various scenarios.</p>

<p>5G CONNI (Athonet (HPE-IT), CEA, CNIT)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: Private 5G and edge computing solutions for connected industries and future smart factories in Europe. Relevance to Project & Key differences: 5G CONNI integrated in its demonstrational setup some O-RAN, core network, and edge computing solutions that may be extended and adapted to 6G-GOALS's PoC on collaborative robots, which considers an industrial scenario with similar motivating use cases as those of 5G CONNI.</p>
<p>GreenEdge (ICL, CEA)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: Taming the environmental impact of mobile networks through green edge-computing platforms. Relevance to Project & Key differences: GreenEdge addresses the challenges of sustainable computing at the network Edge, targeting to minimise the footprint associated with modern communication and computation systems. 6G-GOALS will go beyond the approach explored in GreenEdge since one of the key outcomes of semantic-oriented communications is to notably reduce the quantity and frequency of data being generated, communicated and processed, while preserving the capability of transferring the needed information to accomplish a task. 6G-GOALS will interact with the GreenEdge project and feed activities in WP2 to identify realistic use cases and ML consumption models to test the effectiveness of semantic communications and check its impact in terms of sustainability.</p>
<p>IntellIoT (AAU)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: IntellIoT has developed a general framework for computation, communication, and trustworthiness in distributed IoT environments, applicable to agriculture, healthcare, manufacturing, energy, construction, and smart city. Relevance to Project & Key difference: The general architecture for distributed intelligence and disaggregated network can be applied to the IoT use cases of 6G-GOALS, helping to develop a novel AI-enabled semantic and goal-oriented system architecture for machine-oriented traffic.</p>
<p>WindMill (AAU)</p>	<p>Main Outcome: WindMill has investigated ML techniques for wireless system design, studying methods for radio resource management, strategies for network multi-objective optimisation, and also exploring hierarchical and distributed learning architectures. Relevance to Project & Key difference: The ML-based network optimisation strategies investigated in WindMill can serve as a basis for developing an AI-based framework for network control and resource optimisation. Aligned with the 6G-GOALS objectives, such a framework must be tailored specifically to the semantic and goal-oriented paradigm, going beyond the conventional communication paradigm adopted by WindMill.</p>

4.3 Other Related Initiatives

Table 4-2 highlights various national initiatives related to the project, specifying their geographical regions and the consortium partners involved. Additionally, the table includes a brief description of each initiative and suggests how these projects could complement 6G-GOALS by providing useful inputs.

Table 4-2 Other related initiatives

Project name & Overlapping partners (if any)	Region	Description and relation to the current project
RESTART -NETWIN (CNIT, HPE-IT) 	Italy	NETWIN shares with 6G-GOALS an AI/ML-based approach for network optimisation. Indeed, NETWIN leverages AI and networking in designing ML strategies for 1) guiding autonomous networks able to handle the complexity of future telecommunications with minimum human intervention, 2) designing network architectures able to promote deployment of delay-sensitive and energy-constrained intelligent services. The project focuses on AI/ML approaches running at the edge/cloud for delay-sensitive applications and minimum energy consumption.
RESTART -SUPER (CNIT, HPE-IT, TIM) 	Italy	SUPER aims to support advanced virtualized services in scenarios where real-time performance, QoS, QoE are required. This is achieved by providing a programmable network that is flexible, reliable and capable of meeting the communication requirements of each end user/service. The intelligent programmability of the network envisaged by SUPER is coherent with and complementary to 6G-GOALS's objectives in terms of intelligent management of network resources.
UNICO – Open 6G (NEC) 	Spain	Open6G provides AI solutions that run at schedulers, controllers, and orchestrators across network domains, for de-facto managing the core and RAN part of the network infrastructure. It shares with 6G-GOALS's WP5 such an AI-based approach for network resource management.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the dissemination and standardisation action plan for the 6G-GOALS project. The key objective of 6G-GOALS is to leverage the consortium's research activities to influence the development of relevant standards and to enrich ongoing discussions within major industry associations about the evolution of mobile technologies towards 6G.

The document begins with a detailed dissemination plan that highlights strategies to raise awareness and understanding of the project's outcomes among the wider public and specific target audiences. This plan includes engaging with international forums, publishing research findings in high-impact journals, and participating in conferences to ensure broad dissemination and utilisation of the project's technical achievements.

The standardisation section maps out a roadmap involving pertinent standardisation bodies such as 3GPP, O-RAN, and ETSI. The project aims to contribute to these bodies by observing activities in existing standards, deriving necessary features from the 6G-GOALS use cases, identifying existing gaps, and recommending possible solutions. The involvement with these bodies is crucial for integrating semantic communication and AI-enabled learning into future 6G networks.

Additionally, the document highlights the importance of collaboration with other 6G-SNS JU initiatives. By interacting with other projects and initiatives, 6G-GOALS aims to leverage their findings to enhance its own work on semantic communications, improve network efficiency, and address emerging application requirements.

Looking forward, 6G-GOALS will continue to advocate for the creation of specific Industry Specification Groups (ISGs) on semantics and goal-oriented communication within ETSI, or the inclusion of this topic within current ISGs. This will ensure a better impact by capitalizing on the existing workforce, organisational structure, and extensive network of partners.

The next key deliverables, "D7.4 Intermediate dissemination and standardisation activity report" due at month 18 (M18), and "D7.6 Final dissemination, communication and standardisation activity report" at month 36 (M36), will further detail the progress and impact of 6G-GOALS on the standardisation landscape. These reports will provide comprehensive insights into how the project's innovations are being integrated into global standards, paving the way for the next generation of mobile networks.

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